

16th AgroStat Conference (AgroStat 2024):

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

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PREFACE

Dear Colleagues,

The AgroStat biannual series of conference are driven by the Agro-Industry Group of the French Statistical Society (SFdS), which is a non-profit organisation bringing together researchers, engineers, teachers and statistics users (<https://www.sfds.asso.fr>). The 16th Edition of the AgroStat Conference (AgroStat 2024) will take place from the 3th to 6th September 2024 in the city of Bragança, Portugal, hosted and organised by the Polytechnic Institute of Bragança (IPB).

Bragança is a typically-Portuguese old town (Romanic origin dates back to the 10th century), located by the Natural Park of Montesinho – one of the wildest forest zones of Europe – and the Douro Valley – the third oldest protected wine region in the world; and surrounded by traditional villages of a distinctive rustic beauty. Bragança houses several traditional industries producing a myriad of local foods, such as cheese, fermented meats, wine, chestnuts and honey, which provide substantial economic sustainability to the region.

The AgroStat 2024 conference will reunite internationally recognised researchers and industrial organisations representatives, to take stock of advances in statistics, express their needs and to anticipate future challenges. The AgroStat 2024 conference will provide engineers, modellers, statisticians, developers and end-users, a unique opportunity to exchange knowledge and prospects around novel statistical methods applied to agri-food and sensory sciences. We expect to gather a significant number of delegates to participate in a comprehensive scientific programme that includes 5 keynote lectures, and oral communications, allocated in sessions focusing on the following themes: Sensometrics, Chemometrics, Experimental designs, Process control, Risk analysis, Big Data and Software tools.

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Keywords: Soft goat cheese; *L. monocytogenes*; Predictive microbiology

MODELING THE INHIBITION OF *LISTERIA MONOCYTOGENES* GROWTH IN FISH PRODUCTS WITH LACTIC ACID BACTERIA STRAINS

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The present study aimed to evaluate the potential of several lactic acid bacteria strains, isolated from fish products, as bioprotective cultures against *Listeria monocytogenes* in vacuum-packed, cold-stored fish products. These strains demonstrated their ability to control the growth of *L. monocytogenes* over 21 days of storage and to lower the pH of the medium. To explain the inhibitory effects of the selected lactic acid bacteria on *L. monocytogenes*, microbial interaction was assessed using adapted mathematical models. The kinetic parameters of growth for both microorganisms in monocultures and cocultures were estimated.

The results demonstrate the efficacy of the studied strains in controlling pathogen growth in fish products, achieving an inhibition rate exceeding 40%. The proposed modeling approach aims to reduce the risk of listeriosis associated with the consumption of cold-stored products. It can contribute to establishing a strategy based on bioprotective cultures for fish products.

Keywords: Lactic acid bacteria; Biopreservation; Fish products; *Listeria monocytogenes*; Modeling

ADVANCEMENTS IN BIOMETRIC TECHNIQUES FOR MOROCCAN ARGAN GROVE GOATS

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Biometrics, the science of identifying individuals based on unique physical or behavioral traits, has gained prominence in various fields, including agriculture and animal husbandry. This study highlights the use of biometric techniques in goats, focusing on their importance for breed identification, health monitoring, and livestock management. Goats possess distinctive biometric features such as facial patterns, iris structures, ear shapes, and body measurements, which can be effectively utilized for individual identification. Employing advanced technologies like image processing, machine learning, and 3D scanning allows for the precise and non-invasive capture and analysis of these traits.

Biometric systems offer significant benefits, including enhanced traceability, improved breeding programs, and the prevention of livestock theft and fraud. Moreover, biometric data play a crucial role in health monitoring by enabling early disease detection and optimizing management practices. This emerging field promises to advance goat production systems, contribute to animal welfare, and promote sustainable livestock management practices.

Future research aims to refine the accuracy of biometric identification systems and integrate biometric data with other agricultural technologies for comprehensive livestock management solutions. This work underscores the potential of biometric technologies to revolutionize goat farming, particularly in Moroccan argan groves, fostering advancements in breed improvement, health surveillance, and overall livestock management.

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Keywords: Biometric identification; Goats; Animal welfare; Sustainable livestock management

EVALUATION OF THE SAFETY AND QUALITY OF THE TUNISIAN AGRO-PASTORAL DAIRY PRODUCT "SMEN"

Zeineb Jrad

This study was carried out to determine the typicality of agropastoral dairy product from Béni Khédache region of southern Tunisia, which is Smen, prepared in the traditional way. Smen is a spontaneously fermented clarified butter fat produced in households. For the first time, this study aimed to evaluate the nutritional value, microbial quality, sensorial properties and oxidative stability of goat milk Smen.

To reach this goal, Smen samples (final dairy products) from goat raised in agropastoral systems, were collected and analyzed. The results showed that Smen presented a low pH and aw values (5.25 ± 0.19 and 0.619 ± 0.01 , respectively) but were very viscous (366.66 ± 35.11 cP) and fatty ($91.474 \pm 0.96\%$ of fat content). The evaluation of colour parameters showed the yellow intensity of Smen samples ($b^* = 38,66 \pm 0,04$). The resistance to oxidation of Smen samples was studied by measuring Peroxide value (PV), Thiobarbituric acid (TBA), Free Fatty Acid (FFA), Specific absorptivity at 232 and 270 (K232 and K270) values and oxidation induction time in the Rancimat. Results illustrated that it has moderate stability due to its manufacturing process and to the addition of a mixture of herbs called “natural preservative”.

The characterization of the mixture confirmed its contribution to the quality of the Smen studied. Smen is a microbiologically safe product, and lactic acid bacteria (LAB) are the dominant microorganisms. Likewise, the hedonic test demonstrated consumer's attraction to artisanal products.